

Space-Based Assessment of Banditry and its Nexus with Ungoverned Spaces in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The persistent rise in banditry within Niger State, Nigeria, has significantly threatened human security, livelihoods, and critical infrastructure. This study examines the spatial relationship between banditry and ungoverned spaces, which serve as operational enclaves for armed groups. Spatial analysis of security infrastructure reveals uneven distribution and limited coverage, particularly in high-risk rural areas. Kernel density estimation (KDE) was used to generate banditry hotspot maps, which indicate high concentrations of incidents—such as abductions, armed clashes, and attacks—along the northwestern axis, notably in Muya, Shiroro, Rafi, Gurara, Mokwa, and Mariga. Emerging risk zones were also identified in Kontagora, Wushishi, Gurara, and Lapai. The study further highlights the exposure of vulnerable elements, including settlements, markets, schools, healthcare facilities, and transportation networks, to banditry activities. Findings reveal a strong spatial correlation between ungoverned spaces, inadequate security presence, and the intensity of attacks. The study concludes that integrating geospatial intelligence into security planning, alongside strategic deployment and continuous surveillance, is critical for mitigating banditry and enhancing security governance in Niger State.

Keywords: banditry, ungoverned spaces, GIS, hotspot analysis, security infrastructure, remote sensing, Niger State

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Introduction

According to Ojo (2020), warlords, religious fanatics, and tribal self-defence groups can thrive in ungoverned areas with minimal official monitoring or an uncoordinated state presence, managed by informal networks and hybrid structures. This further highlights how poor governance in these areas encourages the illegal transfer of weapons and ammunition, explosives-making materials, illegal drugs, and foreign machinery. These locations also serve as havens for both bandits and armed groups. In Nigeria, the poor forest governance and the upsurge in cattle banditry in northern Nigeria demonstrates the ways in which weak forest governance yields ungoverned forest spaces that currently provide dwelling places for bandits, Boko Haram insurgents, cattle rustlers, and several criminal groups in northern Nigeria. Weapons and arms flowing within these conflict zones are smuggled in through Nigeria's unmanned and porous borders into the hands of criminal groups. Until the Nigerian state pays attention to territories that are under-governed or poorly governed, it will be challenging to defeat banditry, terrorism, and Fulani militancy. Armed banditry, which is rapidly increasing and endangering the security of people and property in Nigeria, is one of many security issues plaguing the country (Adeniyi et al., 2023; Olapeju & Peter, 2021; Kugbayi & Adegbam, 2023). The level at which bandits operate within the landscape of Nigeria, particularly the northwest region, is a matter of concern due to kidnapping, maiming of people, loss of lives, population displacements, loss of cattle, and disruption of socio-economic activities in general. This has brought an atmosphere of uncertainty, posing a sizeable security threat to the Northwest region as well as Nigeria as a whole. Niger State shares borders with some of the northwest states, such as Zamfara, where bandits have taken over mining fields, and Kaduna, where a kidnapping spree persists. According to Mohammed and Oyinloye (2023), armed banditry is primarily a technique of acquiring resources and money through criminal activity rather than ideology.

Literature Review

The growing body of literature on insecurity in Nigeria highlights the complex and evolving nature of threats such as terrorism, insurgency, and banditry, as well as the limitations of existing countermeasures. Much of this scholarship has focused on the Boko Haram insurgency, providing a useful analytical foundation for understanding broader patterns of insecurity across the country. Scholars have identified structural, socio-economic, and governance-related factors as key drivers of insecurity. For instance, Olufunmilade (2017) attributes the rise of Boko Haram to weak governance, poverty, and ideological radicalization. Similarly, Ani and Chukwu (2014) argue that Nigeria's counterterrorism operations have been undermined by institutional inefficiencies, poor coordination among security agencies, and inadequate intelligence frameworks. These systemic challenges are further emphasized by Falode (2016), who characterizes the Boko Haram conflict as an asymmetric war in which insurgents exploit difficult terrain and mobility advantages to evade conventional military responses.

Strategic responses to insecurity have also been widely debated in the literature. Falode (2019) advocates for a hybrid doctrine that integrates conventional military operations with intelligence-led and community-based approaches, emphasizing the need for flexibility in counterinsurgency efforts. In the same vein, Eji (2016) calls for a fundamental rethinking of Nigeria's counterterrorism strategy, highlighting the importance of technological integration, intelligence enhancement, and civil-military cooperation. Murtala Wazeer (2020) further identifies persistent operational challenges, including inadequate logistics, weak inter-agency collaboration, and the existence of safe havens for armed groups. These safe havens, often located in remote and inaccessible areas, reinforce the importance of spatial factors in shaping insecurity dynamics.

The concept of ungoverned spaces is therefore critical to understanding the persistence of insecurity in Nigeria. Such

spaces are typically characterized by weak state presence, poor infrastructure, and limited surveillance, creating enabling environments for criminal and insurgent activities. Armed groups, including bandits, exploit these areas as operational bases for planning and executing attacks while avoiding detection. This spatial dimension of insecurity remains insufficiently addressed in traditional security approaches, which tend to prioritize reactive measures over proactive territorial monitoring.

Recent studies have increasingly highlighted the potential of geospatial technologies in addressing security challenges. Jerumeh (2024) demonstrates the utility of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in mapping the spatial distribution of household food insecurity in Nigeria, illustrating how spatial analysis can support targeted interventions and policy planning. Although focused on food security, the methodological approach underscores the relevance of GIS in analyzing complex and spatially distributed phenomena, including insecurity.

In a similar context, Bello (2025) emphasizes the growing importance of space technology and geospatial intelligence in enhancing national security and governance in Africa. The study argues that the integration of satellite imagery, remote sensing, and spatial analytics can significantly improve situational awareness and facilitate evidence-based decision-making. Supporting this position, Tella (2022) examines Nigeria's space programme and its application in counterterrorism, demonstrating how satellite technologies have been utilized to monitor and track Boko Haram activities in remote areas. These findings highlight the potential of space-based tools in overcoming the limitations of conventional surveillance methods, particularly in hard-to-reach and ungoverned environments. Despite these advancements, there remains a notable gap in the application of geospatial technologies to the study of banditry, especially in north-central Nigeria. Existing studies have largely concentrated on insurgency in the northeastern region, with limited attention to the spatial

dynamics of banditry and its relationship with ungoverned spaces. Furthermore, there is insufficient integration of hotspot analysis, security infrastructure assessment, and vulnerability mapping within a unified analytical framework. This study addresses these gaps by employing remote sensing and GIS-based techniques to examine the spatial relationship between banditry and ungoverned spaces in Niger State. By integrating hotspot mapping, proximity analysis, and infrastructure assessment, the research provides a comprehensive spatial perspective on insecurity. In doing so, it contributes to the growing call for technology-driven, proactive, and evidence-based approaches to security management in Nigeria (Bello, 2025; Tella, 2022).

Space-based technology remains underutilized despite its potential in addressing complex security challenges. Geospatial technology and GIS applications for mapping areas of insecurity are rapidly developing but face technical, operational, and institutional limitations. This study explores how space technology can serve as analytical tools to reduce crime in ungoverned spaces and define the relationship between banditry and ungoverned areas in Niger State, Nigeria. The main objective of this study is to assess the spatial relationship between banditry and ungoverned spaces in Niger State using space-based analytical tools. Specific objectives include:

1. Identify and map ungoverned spaces within Niger State.
2. Analyze the spatial distribution of security infrastructure across the study area.
3. Map and classify banditry hotspots within Niger State.
4. Identify vulnerable elements exposed to banditry-related attacks.

5. Examine the relationship between security infrastructure distribution and banditry activities.

Research Methodology and Data Sources

This study adopts a geospatial analytical research design, integrating remote sensing, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and spatial statistical techniques to examine the relationship between banditry and ungoverned spaces in Niger State, Nigeria. The approach is grounded in the growing application of GIS in security and crime analysis, where spatial patterns and relationships are used to inform decision-making. It combines both quantitative spatial analysis and geospatial modelling techniques to identify patterns of insecurity, assess the distribution of security infrastructure, and evaluate the exposure of vulnerable elements. This aligns with contemporary approaches that emphasize the use of spatial intelligence in addressing security challenges and counterterrorism. In addition, both primary and secondary geospatial datasets were used to ensure a comprehensive and multi-source analytical framework.

- **Satellite Imagery and Remote Sensing Data:** Sentinel-2 multispectral satellite imagery was used to derive land use and land cover (LULC) classifications and vegetation indices. The imagery, with a spatial resolution of 10–20 meters, enabled the identification of dense vegetation and forested areas that potentially serve as ungoverned spaces. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was computed to distinguish between vegetated and non-vegetated surfaces; a method widely applied in spatial analysis for environmental and security assessments.
- **Conflict and Security Data:** Banditry incident data were obtained from the Armed Conflict Location and Event Data (ACLED) database for the period 2021–2023. These data include georeferenced records of

violent events such as kidnappings, armed clashes, and attacks, which were used to generate hotspot maps and spatial density patterns.

- **Ancillary Geospatial Data:** Additional datasets included administrative boundaries, road networks, settlement data, and terrain information (Digital Elevation Models). These datasets were used to support proximity analysis, accessibility modelling, and spatial overlay operations.
- **Security Infrastructure Data:** Data on the location of police stations and correctional facilities were collected and georeferenced using Global Positioning System (GPS) techniques and secondary government sources. This enabled the assessment of spatial distribution and coverage of security assets.
- **Participatory and Field Data:** Field observations and GPS data collection were incorporated to validate spatial datasets and improve accuracy. The study also draws on participatory GIS principles, which emphasize the integration of local knowledge into spatial analysis for improved reliability and contextual understanding.

Data Processing and Analysis

- **Image Preprocessing and Classification:** Satellite imagery was preprocessed through atmospheric correction, radiometric calibration, and cloud masking to ensure data quality. Supervised classification techniques were applied to categorize land cover into classes such as forest, shrubland, water bodies, and built-up areas. This approach is consistent with GIS-based environmental and spatial inequality studies in Nigeria.

- Identification of Ungoverned Spaces: Ungoverned spaces were delineated using a combination of NDVI thresholds, distance from settlements, and accessibility analysis. Areas with high vegetation density, low population presence, and poor road connectivity were classified as potential ungoverned zones.
- Hotspot and Density Analysis: Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) was employed to identify spatial clusters of banditry incidents. This technique enabled the visualization of high-risk areas and the intensity of attacks across the study area, consistent with established crime mapping methodologies.
- Proximity and Network Analysis: Proximity analysis was conducted to evaluate distances between banditry hotspots and security infrastructure. Network analysis was further applied to assess accessibility to affected areas based on road networks, identifying regions with delayed response potential.
- Overlay and Spatial Correlation Analysis: Multiple spatial layers—including ungoverned spaces, banditry hotspots, and security infrastructure—were overlaid to examine their relationships. This enabled the identification of spatial mismatches and areas of high vulnerability.
- Vulnerability Mapping: Critical assets such as settlements, schools, healthcare facilities, and markets were mapped and analyzed in relation to hotspot zones. This approach supports targeted intervention planning and aligns with GIS applications in socio-spatial vulnerability assessment.

Analytical Framework

The study adopts an integrated geospatial intelligence framework, combining environmental, infrastructural, and security datasets to provide a holistic understanding of insecurity. This framework is consistent with emerging perspectives that emphasize the role of space-based technologies in national security and governance. By leveraging GIS and remote sensing tools, the study moves beyond traditional descriptive analyses to provide predictive and spatially explicit insights into the dynamics of banditry and ungoverned spaces.

Results and Discussion

Spatial Distribution of Ungoverned Spaces

The analysis revealed that ungoverned spaces in Niger State are predominantly concentrated along the state's peripheral and border regions, particularly in areas adjoining Kaduna, Kebbi, Kwara, and Bénin Republic. These areas are characterized by dense vegetation, rugged terrain, and limited accessibility, as confirmed by high normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) values derived from Sentinel-2 imagery. The spatial pattern indicates that these zones are largely disconnected from major settlements and road networks, reinforcing their classification as low-governance areas. This finding supports existing literature that associates ungoverned spaces with weak state presence and limited surveillance capacity. The persistence of such areas suggests that environmental and infrastructural constraints play a critical role in shaping security vulnerabilities. From a geospatial perspective, the clustering of ungoverned spaces along border regions also highlights the strategic advantage they provide to armed groups, enabling cross-border mobility and evasion of security forces. This spatial configuration underscores the need for border-sensitive security strategies and continuous environmental monitoring.

Identification of Ungoverned Spaces

Ungoverned spaces are concentrated along borders with Kaduna, Kebbi, Kwara, and Bénin Republic. NDVI analysis confirmed these areas as densely vegetated and remote, providing operational advantages for bandits.

Fig. 1: Base map showing the location of ungoverned spaces in Niger State. Source: ACLED Data (2025), processed using ArcMap.

Fig. 2: Map of ungoverned spaces in Niger State. Source: ACLED Data (2025), processed using ArcMap.

Distribution of Security Infrastructure

The spatial distribution of security infrastructure across Niger State reveals significant imbalances. The analysis shows that police stations and correctional facilities are sparsely distributed, with large inter-station distances ranging from approximately 12 km to over 130 km. Most security installations are concentrated in urban and semi-urban centers, leaving vast rural and forested areas with

minimal or no security presence. This uneven distribution creates security vacuums, particularly in remote locations where banditry incidents are most prevalent. The findings suggest that the current configuration of security infrastructure is not aligned with the spatial realities of insecurity. Rather than being positioned in high-risk zones, many facilities are located in relatively secure areas, thereby limiting their operational effectiveness. This spatial mismatch reduces response efficiency and allows bandits to operate with relative impunity in underserved regions.

Fig. 3: Map of Security infrastructures as related to banditry in Niger state. Source: ACLED Data (2025), processed using ArcMap

Banditry Hotspots and Spatial Patterns

Hotspot analysis using kernel density estimation (KDE) identified high concentrations of banditry incidents in the northeastern and central parts of Niger State, particularly in local government areas such as Rafi, Shiroro, Mariga, Kontagora, and Wushishi. These hotspots exhibit strong spatial clustering, indicating that banditry is not randomly distributed but rather concentrated in specific high-risk zones.

Fig. 4: Map of vulnerable elements of banditry in Niger State. Sources Acled Data (2025), processed using ArcMap

Vulnerable Elements

Targets include settlements, schools, farmlands, security infrastructure, healthcare facilities, roads, and markets. Spatial mapping highlights areas where government interventions are critical (Mohammed & Oyinloye, 2023).

Table 1: Security stations and banditry distance data

	Security station	LGA	Closest banditry activity	Distance (km)
1	Mashegu Police Division	Mashegu	attack	11.48
2	Lagun Police Station	Lagun	attack	2.3
3	Nasko Police Station	Magama	attack	2.6
4	Fuka Police	Munya	attack	7.5
5	Police Outpost Lefu	Lapai	attack	37.7
6	Beri Police Station	Paikoro	attack	1.2
7	Fogbe Police Outpost	Lapai	attack	11.2
8	Out Post Police Station Nassarawa	Borgu	attack	13.3
9	Kabo Police Station	Gurara	armed clash	0.32
10	Dukku Central Police Station	Rijau	armed clash	17.6
11	Mashegu Police Division	Mashegu	attack	11.2
12	Police Outpost Jaagi	Mokwa	attack	24.3
13	Paiko Police Station	Paikoro	attack	1.01
14	Kataeregi Police Station	Bosso	abduction	30.1
15	Far Doki Police Station	Paikoro	armed clash and abduction	17.6
16	Erena Divisional Police Station	Shiroro	attack	0.2
17	Kawo Out Station	Magama	attack	18.6
18	Kuta Division Police Station Kobwa	Shiroro	attack	1.6
19	Kpanbo Police Outpost	Lavun	attack	25.3
20	Malle Police Outpost	Borgu	attack	20.2
21	Bargi Police Station	Mariga	air/drone strike	6.7

Vulnerable elements map. Source: Aced, 2025.

Vulnerable Elements and Exposure Analysis

The mapping of vulnerable elements—including settlements, schools, healthcare facilities, markets, and transportation networks—reveals a high degree of exposure to banditry in identified hotspot areas. Many of these critical assets are located within proximity to high-risk zones, making them frequent targets of attacks. The spatial overlap between vulnerable elements and banditry hotspots indicates a direct threat to human security and socio-economic stability. For instance, attacks on schools and healthcare facilities disrupt essential services, while the destruction of markets and farmlands undermines livelihoods and food security. This finding reinforces the need for targeted protection strategies and highlights the importance of integrating vulnerability mapping into security planning. It also demonstrates the value of GIS in identifying priority areas for intervention and resource allocation.

Relationship Between Ungoverned Spaces, Security Infrastructure, and Banditry

Overlay analysis reveals a strong spatial relationship between ungoverned spaces and banditry hotspots. Most high-density incident areas are located either within or in close proximity to identified ungoverned zones. This suggests that such spaces serve as operational bases for bandits, providing concealment, logistical support, and strategic advantage.

Furthermore, the analysis shows a clear spatial mismatch between the location of security infrastructure and areas of high banditry activity. In many cases, hotspots are situated far from the nearest security installations, resulting in delayed response times and reduced deterrence. This finding aligns with the broader argument that ineffective spatial planning and inadequate integration of geospatial intelligence contribute to persistent insecurity. It also highlights the limitations of reactive security approaches, which often fail to address the underlying spatial

drivers of conflict. The results demonstrate that banditry in Niger State is not only a security issue but also a spatial phenomenon influenced by environmental, infrastructural, and governance factors. The integration of geospatial technologies in this study provides empirical evidence to support the adoption of proactive, data-driven security strategies.

Implications for Security Planning

The findings of this study have significant implications for security planning and policy formulation. First, they emphasize the need for a shift from conventional, reactive approaches to proactive, spatially informed strategies. Second, they highlight the importance of aligning security infrastructure with identified risk zones to improve operational efficiency.

Additionally, the study demonstrates the potential of geospatial technologies as decision-support tools for monitoring, prediction, and intervention. By leveraging GIS and remote sensing, security agencies can enhance situational awareness, optimize resource allocation, and develop targeted responses to emerging threats. Overall, the results underscore the critical role of spatial analysis in understanding and addressing insecurity in Nigeria, particularly in regions characterized by ungoverned spaces.

Fig. 5: Security vs. banditry overlay map. Source: Aclcd Data (2025), processed using ArcMap

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has demonstrated that banditry in Niger State is fundamentally a spatially structured security challenge, strongly influenced by the distribution of ungoverned spaces, environmental characteristics, and the uneven allocation of security infrastructure.

Using remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS)-based analytical techniques, the research established a clear spatial correlation between high-density vegetation zones, low accessibility, and the concentration of banditry incidents. The findings reveal that ungoverned spaces—primarily located along border regions and characterized by dense vegetation and weak state presence—serve as strategic operational bases for bandits. These areas provide concealment, mobility advantages, and reduced risk of detection, thereby facilitating sustained criminal activities. The application of NDVI and land cover classification techniques confirmed the environmental suitability of these zones for illicit operations, reinforcing the argument that terrain and land use patterns are critical determinants of insecurity.

Furthermore, the study identified a significant spatial mismatch between banditry hotspots and the distribution of security infrastructure. Security installations are largely concentrated in urban centers, leaving high-risk rural and forested areas underserved. This imbalance contributes to delayed response times, limited deterrence, and the persistence of insecurity in vulnerable regions. Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) and proximity analyses further highlighted the clustering of attacks in areas with minimal security presence, underscoring the limitations of conventional deployment strategies.

The integration of vulnerability mapping into the analysis also revealed the extent to which critical assets—including settlements, schools, healthcare facilities, and markets—are exposed to banditry. The spatial overlap between these elements and identified hotspots indicates a direct threat to human security, socioeconomic stability, and regional development. This reinforces the need for targeted, location-specific interventions that prioritize high-risk zones.

Importantly, this study advances the discourse on insecurity in Nigeria by demonstrating the analytical and operational value of geospatial technologies in security planning. By combining

satellite imagery, GIS-based modelling, and spatial statistics, the research provides a data-driven framework for understanding and addressing the dynamics of banditry. The findings support the growing consensus that effective security management in complex environments requires the integration of space-based intelligence, predictive analytics, and spatial decision-support systems. Addressing banditry in Niger State requires a paradigm shift from reactive, conventional approaches to proactive, spatially informed security strategies. The adoption of geospatial intelligence, coupled with strategic infrastructure deployment and community engagement, offers a viable pathway for mitigating insecurity and enhancing governance in ungoverned spaces. This study therefore contributes not only to academic knowledge but also to policy and operational frameworks aimed at achieving sustainable security outcomes in Nigeria.

Regular land use and land cover (LULC) mapping is essential for continuously identifying and monitoring ungoverned spaces within Niger State. These areas are often characterized by dense vegetation, difficult terrain, and limited human presence, making them ideal hideouts for bandits. By institutionalizing periodic geospatial assessments using satellite imagery and GIS tools, government agencies can detect environmental changes, track the expansion or reduction of forested areas, and identify newly emerging isolated zones. This proactive approach will enable security planners to anticipate potential threats rather than reacting after attacks occur. Furthermore, integrating temporal analysis into mapping efforts will help reveal patterns of movement and seasonal variations in bandit activities.

The strategic deployment of security personnel and infrastructure should be guided by spatial intelligence derived from hotspot analysis. Rather than clustering security installations in urban or already secure areas, there is a need to establish forward operating bases, mobile patrol units, and surveillance outposts in proximity to identified banditry hotspots. This will reduce response

time during attacks and serve as a deterrent to criminal activities. In addition, adopting a decentralized security framework—supported by local intelligence networks—can enhance situational awareness and improve operational efficiency. Strategic placement should also consider accessibility, road networks, and proximity to vulnerable communities to maximize impact.

Identifying and mapping vulnerable elements such as schools, healthcare facilities, markets, religious centers, and settlements is critical for effective emergency planning and response. By creating a comprehensive geospatial database of these assets, security agencies and emergency responders can prioritize protection efforts and allocate resources more efficiently. This mapping should be integrated into an early warning system that enables rapid deployment of security forces when threats are detected near high-risk locations. Additionally, understanding the spatial relationship between vulnerable elements and banditry hotspots will help in designing targeted interventions, such as community-based protection strategies and infrastructure reinforcement.

Leverage space-based technology for surveillance. The adoption of space-based technologies, including satellite surveillance, drones, and remote sensing systems, offers a transformative approach to tackling insecurity in ungoverned spaces. These technologies provide real-time or near-real-time data that can be used to monitor suspicious movements, detect encampments, and track changes in terrain that may indicate criminal activity. Integrating these tools into existing security frameworks will enhance intelligence gathering and support evidence-based decision-making. Moreover, the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for reconnaissance missions can significantly reduce risks to personnel while improving coverage of hard-to-reach areas.

Public awareness plays a vital role in strengthening community resilience against banditry. Educating residents about security risks, early warning signs, and appropriate reporting channels can foster a collaborative security environment. Community

engagement initiatives, including town hall meetings, local radio programs, and sensitization campaigns, should be implemented to encourage vigilance and cooperation with security agencies. When citizens are well-informed, they are more likely to provide timely and actionable intelligence, which is crucial for preventing attacks. Building trust between communities and security forces is also essential for ensuring sustained collaboration.

Banditry in Niger State is not an isolated phenomenon but is closely linked to activities in neighboring states and across international borders. Therefore, fostering strong inter-state and cross-border collaboration is critical for addressing the problem effectively. This includes intelligence sharing, joint security operations, and harmonized policy frameworks among affected states such as Kaduna, Kebbi, Zamfara, and Kwara. Establishing regional security task forces and communication platforms will enhance coordination and reduce operational gaps that bandits often exploit. Additionally, collaboration with border security agencies will help curb the influx of illegal arms and restrict the movement of criminal groups across porous borders.

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